

ASSESSMENT OF ENDOTHELIAL DYSFUNCTION BIOMARKERS (ET-1 AND ENOS) IN THE CONTEXT OF OVERWEIGHT AND ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION

U.I. Usmanova¹, U.Kh. Musashaykhov¹, D.A. Nabiyeva²

Andijan State Medical Institute, Andijan¹

Tashkent Medical Academy, Tashkent²

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Abstract. *This study evaluated the levels of molecular biomarkers of endothelial dysfunction – endothelin-1 (ET-1) and endothelial nitric oxide synthase (eNOS) – in individuals with excess body weight and arterial hypertension. Clinical and laboratory assessments demonstrated that elevated ET-1 levels and decreased eNOS concentrations indicate disruption of endothelial balance and progression of the pathological process. A comprehensive analysis of these biomarkers may serve as a valuable diagnostic tool for early detection of endothelial dysfunction and evaluation of metabolic risk factors.*

Keywords: *endothelial dysfunction, ET-1, eNOS, arterial hypertension, obesity.*

Relevance of the problem. One of the most potent endogenous vasoconstrictors and mitogens synthesized by endothelial cells is endothelin-1. II) endothelial nitric oxide synthase (eNOS), a principal enzyme mainly responsible for the synthesis of nitric oxide (NO), an important molecule for endothelium-dependent vasodilation, antiplatelet and antiproliferative effects. The endothelium is an extremely active metabolic entity that is central to the maintenance of vascular tone, which is largely achieved by the control of either vasodilative or vasoconstrictive stimuli [8, 9].

Recently, the role of the vascular endothelium in the pathogenesis of essential arterial hypertension (EAH) has gained significant interest and could be a relevant target for therapy. Several recent scientific studies have confirmed this (Musikhina N.A., 2020; Mustafaeva A.G., 2021; Sofronenko A.V., 2022; Arnaud et al., 2023; Umyagina I.A., 2023). Important pathogenic pathways of ED consist of the activation of the sympathoadrenal and renin-angiotensin-aldosterone systems, reduced production of NO, overexpression of endothelin-1 (ET-1), oxidative

Given the central role of the endothelium in sustaining vascular homeostasis, the search for biomarkers that reflect its functional state, and especially ET-1 and eNOS, is the primary course of action in elucidating the pathogenesis of cardiometabolic diseases [1, 2, 10].

Objective: to study the significance of serum markers of endothelial dysfunction (eNOS, EDN-1) in the formation of arterial hypertension in patients with overweight and obesity.

Materials and methods of the study. Overall, 276 patients were investigated in this clinical trial, further divided into 2 main cohort groups: the main group (n = 171) and control group (n = 105). The control group, matched to the main group by age and sex, included healthy subjects without clinically relevant AH symptoms. These groups were originally formed to explore the pathogenic role of obesity, as a modifiable risk factor, in EAH onset and progression.

These consortia were designed to examine the pathogenic role of obesity as a modifiable risk factor in the development and progression of EAH. In the context of this, the main cohort was

divided into the following groups: individuals with EAH as a main diagnosis but no symptoms of obesity: mean age 61.8 ± 1.46 years (37–71 years); patients with EAH and obesity symptoms: mean age 61.8 ± 1.98 years (44–80 years); patients with obesity (but no clinical evidence of EAH): mean age 44.5 ± 0.00 years (26–62 years).

Every group went through a stepwise, systematic clinical examination. The investigation sought to identify molecular predictors of arterial hypertension and carry out multi-stage analysis of the cardiovascular system. The below were the elements of the study: comprehensive collection of medical history, such as genetic and family history of predisposition to cardiometabolic disease, risk factor (RF) identification, lifestyle evaluation, food consumption, physical activity level, psychological stress, and occurrence of risky behavior; physical and clinical examination, which includes the measurement of vital anthropometric measures (height, weight, and waist circumference), blood pressure (BP) and heart rate (HR), body mass index (BMI) calculation and risk level classification based on obesity criteria; application of enzyme-linked immunosorbent test (ELISA) to determine the blood biomarkers ET-1 and eNOS, endothelial function markers; entering data into Microsoft Excel and subsequently statistically comparing the clinical and laboratory findings that were obtained; In order to evaluate significant associations between the factors under investigation, statistical analysis was performed using the χ^2 (chi-square) test, odds ratios (OR), 95% confidence intervals (CI), and correlation analysis.

Results and discussion. ET-1 and eNOS serum levels were studied in individuals suffering from different clinical conditions to evaluate the contribution of AH and obesity to the dysfunction of endothelium-dependent mechanisms. Figures 1 and 2 show the statistically significant intergroup differences in ET-1 and eNOS levels, which were determined during the analysis.

The eNOS level in patients with EAH (group I) was 1273.47 ± 323.22 pg/ml, and there was a compensatory increase in NO production, while ET-1 level was 16.47 ± 3.49 pg/ml. This may indicate an adaptive endothelial reaction to prevent vasoconstriction and preserve vasodilatation. ET-1 levels rose significantly to 32.34 ± 10.11 pg/ml in patients who had both AH and obesity (group II), denoting more severe ED and potentiated vasoconstrictor mechanisms.

Compensatory function of impaired endothelium is also expressed through the reduction in eNOS levels to 1140.69 ± 213.53 pg/ml.

The concentration of ET-1 in obese but non-EAH (group III) was 26.03 ± 5.21 pg/ml, which corresponded to a moderate level of ED that was weaker than in obesity and AH combined. lowest being 848.21 ± 251.60 pg/ml, this indicates the insufficiency of NO and complete failure of endothelial-dependent vasodilation mechanisms. Chronic inflammatory mechanisms, metabolic derangement, and hyperinsulinemia are likely to be the causes for such alterations.

Figure 1. Average concentrations of ET-1 in blood serum (pg/ml) based on the results for EAH, obesity, and their combined conditions ($n = 171$).

Determining the way ET-1 and eNOS levels vary with comorbid conditions (obesity and EAH), evaluating the pathogenic role of both factors (obesity or EAH) and the dominant factor influencing the severity of ED were among the primary objectives of the study. Based on the findings:

The control value of AH without metabolic imbalance was 16.47 ± 3.49 pg/ml and was the mean level of ET-1 in group I (patients with EAH alone).

In group III (obesity exists but EAH does not): Under the conditions of insulin resistance, hyperleptinemia, and chronic subclinical inflammation, ET-1 levels rose to 26.03 ± 5.21 pg/ml, reflecting increased vasoconstrictor activity and a sign of ED ($p < 0.001$). The highest ET-1 level was found in Group II, which included both obesity and EAH, at 32.34 ± 10.11 pg/ml. It was significantly higher in groups III and I ($p < 0.001$) and their synergistic negative effect due to metabolic and haemodynamic abnormalities account for the findings.

Figure 2. Mean serum eNOS levels (pg/ml) based on the findings in patients with EAH, obesity, and their combination ($n = 171$).

An inverse dynamic was noted when comparing the levels of eNOS. Group I had the highest enzyme level, which was 1273.47 ± 323.22 pg/ml. The preserved endothelial function in isolated AH cases under conditions of compensatory vascular response most likely explains this observation. The eNOS level in group III (obesity but without EAH) was 848.21 ± 251.60 pg/ml, which was a statistically significant decrease from group I ($p < 0.001$). At a mean of 1140.69 ± 213.53 pg/ml, the activity of eNOS was also reduced in group II (obesity and combined EAH). The result indicated a relatively compensated endothelial production of NO against the background of hypertension and was greater than that of group III but significantly less than that of group I ($p < 0.001$).

In addition, a deep negative correlation between ET-1 and eNOS levels was proven by correlation analysis ($r = -0.79$).

Such correlation would indicate that with the aggravation of metabolic disorders, decompensation, or breakdown, of equilibrium between vasoconstrictor and vasodilatory mediators can occur.

Systemic endothelial pathologies arise when the vasoconstrictor action of ET-1 is stronger than NO production reduction.

As a consequence, the stepwise development of thrombogenic disorders, atherosclerosis, and arterial hypertension follows.

Conclusion. According to the findings of the clinical study, both obese and AH patients displayed noticeable alterations of biomarkers including ET-1 and eNOS when ED manifested.

Results showed that a combination of obesity and AH demonstrated the highest degree of ET-1 and reduction in the degree of eNOS, reflecting worsening of ED and higher activity of vasoconstrictor factors.

Correspondingly, reduced levels of eNOS suggest that the endothelial compensation mechanisms are beginning to weaken.

High diagnostic sensitivity of ET-1 and eNOS biomarkers was shown in comparison between groups of these markers. Significant growth in the level of ET-1 and reduction in the level of eNOS, particularly, signify a violation of endothelial function balance in cases where obesity predisposes to the development of AH. Furthermore, the impact of inflammatory and metabolic processes on endothelial function is expressed in the stable negative correlation ($r = -0.79$) between ET-1 and eNOS.

In summary, the multifaceted estimation of ET-1 and eNOS biomarkers is crucial for the early assessment of endothelial dysfunction in arterial hypertension against the background of obesity, the determination of the severity of pathological processes, and prevention of disease progression.

REFERENCES

1. Zimnitskaya O.V. Features of endothelial dysfunction in hypertension // *Medical Alphabet*. – 2019. – Vol. 1, No. 3. – P. 29–33.
2. Ibragimova X.I., Mammaev S.N. The role of endothelin-1 in the pathogenesis of arterial hypertension and its complications // *Clinical Gerontology*. – 2017. – Vol. 1–2. – P. 57–62.
3. Musixina N.A., Gapon L.I., Petelina T.I., Maxneva E.A., Yemeneva I.V. Endothelial dysfunction and heart rhythm variability in arterial hypertension and coronary heart disease // *Arterial Hypertension*. – 2016. – Vol. 22, No. 4. – P. 414–424.
4. Mustafaeva A.G. Interrelationship between endothelial dysfunction and the development of metabolic syndrome complications // *Kazan Medical Journal*. – 2018. – Vol. 99, No. 5. – P. 784–791.
5. Safronenko A.V., Gantsgorn E.V. Endothelial dysfunction in refractory arterial hypertension // *Southern Russia Therapeutic Practice Journal*. – 2021. – Vol. 2, No. 2. – P. 26–33.
6. Umnyagina I.A., Blinova T.V., Straxova L.A., Ivanova Yu.V., Troshin V.V., Kolesov S.A., Fomina Yu.N. The role of endothelin-1 and nitrogen oxide metabolites in diagnosing the risk of arterial hypertension in young and middle-aged individuals working under harmful conditions // *Clinical Laboratory Diagnostics*. – 2021. – No. 9.
7. Arnaud C., Billoir E., de Melo Junior A.F., Pereira S.A., O'Halloran K.D., Monteiro E.C. Cardiovascular and renal dysfunction related to chronic intermittent hypoxia: transition from adaptation to maladaptation // *Journal of Physiology*. – December 2023; 601(24):5553–5577.
8. McMaster W.G., Kirabo A., Madhur M.S., Harrison D.G. Inflammation, immunity, and organ injury related to hypertension // *Circulation Research*. – March 13, 2015; 116(6):1022–1033.
9. Shabrov A.V., Galenko A.S., Uspenskiy Yu.P., Loseva K.A. Methods of diagnosing endothelial dysfunction // *Siberian Medical Newsletter*. – 2021. – Vol. 20, No. 2. – P. 202–209.
10. Timofeev Yu.S., Mikhailova M.A., Djioyeva O.N., Drapkina O.M. The significance of biomarkers in assessing endothelial dysfunction // *Cardiovascular Therapy and Prevention*. – 2024. – Vol. 23, No. 9.